

CHARGE AND STABILITY OF COLLOIDS. PART XIV. EFFECT OF NON-ELECTROLYTES

By A. C. CHATTERJI AND RAM NATH

The effect of non-electrolytes such as propyl, isopropyl and butyl alcohol, glycol, glycerol and acetone on the stability of arsenious sulphide sol has been studied. It has been observed that the variations in the coagulation concentration of an electrolyte and the adsorption of oppositely charged ions of the same electrolyte do not always go hand in hand.

In part II of this series of papers (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 109) the effect of non-electrolytes such as methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, agar agar and gelatin was studied. In this paper the work has been extended and the effect of propyl, isopropyl and butyl alcohol, glycol, glycerol and acetone has been studied from the viewpoint of the variation in the coagulation concentration and the adsorption of oppositely charged ions by the colloidal particles of arsenious sulphide sol.

It has been suggested in the previous paper (*loc. cit.*) that when protection takes place, the charge on the colloid need not necessarily increase appreciably. This view has been confirmed, and as a matter of fact, while stability against coagulation by electrolytes goes on increasing, the adsorption of oppositely charged ions near about the coagulation point instead of increasing actually decreases.

In this paper adsorption of oppositely charged ions by the colloidal particles of arsenious sulphide sol has been measured by the method given in part I of this series of papers (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943; 20, 25) in presence of various non-electrolytes, in varying concentrations, in order to find out how the adsorption varies under different conditions. Under the limitations, as pointed out in the same paper (*loc. cit.*), the charge on the colloidal particles has been calculated from the chemical adsorption alone, on the assumption that the adsorbed ions of the electrolyte displace all ions of the same sign in the electrical double layer.

EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental procedure followed in this paper is the same as given in part I (*loc. cit.*). The coagulation concentrations for a particular sol of known concentration, when propyl and isopropyl alcohols were added in increasing amounts, are given in Table IA and IB respectively.

TABLE IA

Conc. of sol=20.1g./litre.
Sol taken=5 c.c. Total volume=10 c.c.
Time of coagulation=1 hour.

PrOH added (% by volume).	Coagulating conc. of N/80- BaCl ₂ .
0 c.c.	1.9 c.c.
1	2.05
10	2.6
20	5.0
30	5.5

TABLE IB

Conc. of sol=21.94 g/litre.
Sol taken=5 c.c. Total volume=10 c.c.
Time of coagulation=1 hour.

isoPrOH added (% by volume)	Coagulating conc. of N/80- BaCl ₂ .
0 c.c.	2.0 c.c.
1	2.05
10	2.2
15	2.3
20	2.5

From the above tables a stabilisation is observed with propyl alcohol and isopropyl alcohol towards electrolytes. In the following tables the adsorption of oppositely charged ions by the particles of arsenious sulphide sol, when non-electrolytes are added in varying concentrations, are given.

TABLE II

Variation in the adsorption of Ba-ions by the particles of arsenious sulphide sol when propyl alcohol is added in increasing concentrations.

Conc. of the sol=20.01 g./litre. Radius of the particle=75 $\mu\mu$ (by extra polation). Sol taken=200 c.c. Total volume=400 c.c. No. of particles in the sol taken=6.376 $\times 10^{14}$.

Nature of sol.	N/20-BaCl ₂ added.	Adsorption of Baions			Charge <i>e.s.z.</i> $\times 10^6$
		Total.	Physical.	Chemical.	
Sol + water	22 c.c.	.002645 g.	0.01265 g.	0.01380 g.	9.13
Sol + 1c.c. alcohol + water	22	.02710	.01268	.01442	9.54
" + 2 " + "	23	.02690	.01270	.01420	9.39
" + 4 " + "	23	.02657	.01268	.01389	9.19
" + 8 " + "	25	.02610	.01266	.01344	8.89
" + 16 " + "	25	.02487	.01268	.01219	8.06
" + 32 " + "	26	.02410	.01268	.01142	7.55
" + 50 " + "	30	.02308	.01260	.01048	6.93

TABLE III

Variation in the adsorption of Ba-ions by the particles of As_2S_3 sol when isopropyl alcohol is added in increasing conc.

Conc. of the sol=21.94 g./litre. Radius of the particles= $75 \mu\mu$ (by extrapolation).
Sol taken=200 c.c. Total volume=400 c.c. No. of particles in the sol taken= 6.99×10^{14} .

Nature of sol.	N/20-BaCl ₂ added.	Adsorption of Ba-ions			Charge e.s.u. $\times 10^6$.
		Total.	Physical.	Chemical.	
Sol + water	22 c.c.	0.03130 g.	0.01540 g.	0.01590 g.	9.55
Sol + 1c.c. alcohol + water	22	.03331	.01560	.01771	10.65
" + 2 " + "	23	.03154	.01545	.01609	9.70
" + 4 " + "	23	.03131	.01548	.01583	9.54
" + 8 " + "	25	.03048	.01540	.01508	9.09
" + 16 " + "	25	.02930	.01550	.01380	8.32
" + 32 " + "	26	.02871	.01548	.01323	7.98
" + 50 " + "	30	.02810	.01540	.01270	7.66

TABLE IV

Variation in the adsorption of Ba-ions by the particles of As_2S_3 sol when glyccol is added in increasing conc.

Conc. of the sol=18.89 g./litre. Radius of the particle= $75 \mu\mu$ (by extrapolation).
Sol taken=200 c.c. Total volume=400 c.c. No. of particles in the sol taken= 6.02×10^{15} .

Nature of sol.	N/20-BaCl ₂ added.	Adsorption of Ba-ions			Charge e.s.u. $\times 10^6$.
		Total.	Physical.	Chemical.	
Sol + water	22 c.c.	0.02328 g.	0.01102 g.	0.01226 g.	8.60
Sol + 1c.c. glycol + water	22	.02411	.01110	.01301	9.11
" + 2 " + "	23	.02386	.01110	.01276	8.94
" + 4 " + "	25	.02343	.01100	.01243	8.71
" + 8 " + "	25	.02331	.01105	.01226	8.59
" + 16 " + "	26	.02330	.01100	.01230	8.61
" + 32 " + "	30	.02320	.01100	.01220	8.54

TABLE V

Variation in the adsorption of Ba-ions by the particles of As_2S_3 sol when glycerol is added in increasing conc.

Conc. of the sol=20.65 g./litre. Radius of the particle= $75 \mu\mu$ (by extrapolation).
Sol taken=200 c.c. Total volume=400 c.c. No. of particles in the sol taken= 6.58×10^{14} .

Nature of sol.	N/20-BaCl ₂ added.	Adsorption of Ba-ions			Charge e.s.u. $\times 10^6$.
		Total.	Physical.	Chemical.	
Sol + water	22 c.c.	0.02769 g.	0.01293 g.	0.01476 g.	9.46
Sol + 1c.c. glycerol + water	22	.02853	.01300	.01552	9.94
" + 2 " + "	23	.02850	.01300	.01550	9.93
" + 4 " + "	23	.02816	.01298	.01518	9.72
" + 8 " + "	24	—	.01290	—	—
" + 16 " + "	24	.02769	.01302	.01467	9.40
" + 36 " + "	25	.02557	.01300	.01257	8.05
" + 64 " + "	30	.02490	.01300	.01190	7.62

TABLE VI

Variation in the adsorption of Ba-ions by the particles of arsenious sulphide sol when butyl alcohol is added in increasing concentration.

Conc. of the sol=19.48 g./litre. Radius of the particle=75 $\mu\mu$ (by extrapolation).
Sol taken=200 c.c. Total volume=400 c.c. No. of particles in the sol taken= 6.206×10^{14} .

Nature of the sol	N/20-BaCl ₂ added.	Adsorption of Ba-ions		Charge e.s.u. $\times 10^5$.	
		Total.	Physical		Chemical.
Sol + water	22 c.c.	0.02566 g.	0.01275 g.	0.01291g.	8.79
Sol + 1c.c. alcohol + water	22	.02408	.01286	.01122	7.62
" + 2 " + "	23	.02430	.01286	.01144	7.77
" + 4 " + "	23	—	.01286	—	—
" + 8 " + "	24	.02524	.01280	.01244	7.77
" + 10 " + "	26	.02576	.01285	.01291	8.74
" + 13 " + "	26	.02632	.01275	.01357	9.22
" + 16 " + "	30	.02632	.01285	.01347	9.15
" + 24 " + "	30	.02500	.01280	.01220	8.29

TABLE VII

Variation in the adsorption of Ba-ions when acetone is added in increasing concentration.

Conc. of the sol=21.94 g./litre. Radius of the particle=75 $\mu\mu$ (by extrapolation).
Sol taken=200 c.c. Total volume=400 c.c. No. of particles in the sol taken= 6.99×10^{14} .

Nature of the sol.	N/20-BaCl ₂ added	Adsorption of Ba-ions		Charge e.s.u. $\times 10^5$	
		Total.	Physical		Chemical.
Sol + water	23 c.c.	0.03160 g.	0.01613 g	0.01547 g	9.33
Sol + 1/4 c.c. acetone + water	23	.03044	.01610	.01434	8.65
" + 1 " + "	24	—	.01620	—	—
" + 2 " + "	24	.03120	.01620	.01500	9.05
" + 4 " + "	26	.03140	.01613	.01527	9.21
" + 8 " + "	26	.03180	.01621	.01559	9.40
" + 16 " + "	28	.03048	.01630	.01418	9.55
" + 32 " + "	29.5	.03000	.01624	.01376	8.30
" + 50 " + "	30	.02954	.01625	.01319	8.02
" + 64 " + "	32	.02840	.01625	.01215	7.33

DISCUSSION

From the results given in the above tables it can be seen that in the case of propyl and isopropyl alcohol, glycol and glycerol, there is a slight increase on the charge of the colloid, which is then followed by a decrease on the addition of larger amounts of non-electrolyte. In the latter condition the charge continuously falls and goes even below its original value. In the case of acetone and butyl alcohol there is a slight lowering in the initial stages, followed by an increase and then a decrease on the addition of larger amounts of non-electrolytes. In the case of propyl and isopropyl alcohols, however, stability towards coagulation concentration goes on increasing irrespective of the variation of charge, as calculated from the adsorption experiments. Further, it is interesting to note that

when coagulation concentration is plotted against the amount of non-electrolyte added, in case of propyl alcohol there is a rapid increase in stability, whereas in the case of isopropyl alcohol the rate of increase is much slower. The physical adsorption almost remains constant in each case.

Out of the many factors which affect the stability of colloids on the addition of non-electrolytes, the lowering in the dielectric constant and the lowering of the solid-liquid interfacial tension are greatly emphasised. The addition of a non-electrolyte with a lower dielectric constant lowers the dielectrics of the medium. This may affect the stability in three ways : It brings about (i) a greater repulsive force between the colloidal particles on account of which the sol becomes stabilised, (ii) an increased electrical adsorption of the oppositely charged ions by the colloid, which will sensitise the sol, and (3) a repulsion between similarly charged ions, which means that they are less adsorbed and hence sensitisation results. The net effect will depend upon the magnitude of these three factors (cf. Mukherjee and Chaudhury, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 307).

The decrease in interfacial tension increases stability and it is just possible that the charge may be negligible, but due to lowering of interfacial tension stability may be increased, and also a colloid, with a low charge, may be more stable than a colloid with a high charge if its interfacial tension is sufficiently low. This may explain the apparent paradox that though the charge decreases yet the coagulation concentration increases. This will specially be the case with non-electrolytes of lower surface tension.

Thus, from the above it may be seen that if on the addition of the non-electrolyte a diminution of the dielectric constant accompanied by a decrease in the solid-liquid interfacial tension takes place, then we may have stability with not simultaneous increase of the charge on the colloid. But if along with these two effects, increased electrical adsorption of oppositely charged ions by the colloid also takes place, the charge may be lowered. Hence, it is possible to have stability towards electrolytic coagulation accompanied by not much variation in the charge, or even the lowering of the charge of the colloid. The net effect will depend upon the magnitude of these various factors. It appears that in the majority of cases like propyl alcohol, isopropyl alcohol, glycol, and glycerol, stability accompanied by a lowering in the charge is produced.

The initial increase in the charge on the addition of non-electrolytes in small concentrations is indicated by the increase in the 'chemical adsorption'. A clear conception as to how this is brought about, is not yet available. This may be due to the desorption of secondarily charged ions or a decrease in the thickness of the double layer, but certainly cannot be due to an increase in the adsorption of the similarly charged ions, because here no electrolyte is added. Attempts are being made to obtain more data to clear this point.

The initial decrease in charge in the case of acetone and butyl alcohol may be due to some complex formation between the potential bearing ions on the surface of the colloid and the non-electrolyte (cf. Kawjat, *Colloid J.*, 1939, 5, 399).